
APPLICATION OF THE TOOLS OF THE "DIRECT-COSTING" METHOD FOR THE OBJECTIVE EVALUATION OF THE ACTIVITY OF THE RESPONSIBILITY CENTERS

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***Abstract.** Ensuring the basic requirement of a market economy to cover production costs to generate income is impossible without a constant measurement of the resources used in operating activities with their ultimate return in the form of an inflow of economic benefits. The solution of this requirement within the framework of the local management accounting system faces many difficulties, since this system is actually focused on the past, and its entire instrumental and methodological apparatus is subject to clarification of past events. Therefore, the constant implementation of managerial control over responsibility centers by measuring the results of activities carried out in them is a requirement that determines the piloting of the subject to obtain economic efficiency. For the development of the predictive aspect of management accounting, it is necessary to study and creatively apply the best practices of European countries with effective methods for collecting, processing and using information. In this regard, this article focuses on the study of the essence and possibility of using transfer pricing as an objective tool for assessing the activities of production units of agricultural enterprises.*

***Key words:** managerial accounting, direct-costing, centre of responsibility, method to calculations, transfer prices.*

The improvement of the managerial methods and economic relations has greatly increased the responsibility of owners, managers and specialists for the results obtained and for ensuring a profitable business. At the same time, the coverage of costs from revenue - the basic requirement of the market economy - is impossible without the permanent measurement of the means used in production with their final yield in the form of an influx of economic benefits. The solution of this problem within the national accounting system of cost accounting faces many difficulties, because this system is oriented, in fact, towards the past, its entire instrumental and methodical apparatus being subordinated to the elucidation of the committed events. Therefore, the permanent exercise of management control over responsibility

centers, by measuring the results of the activity carried out within them, is the requirement that conditions the piloting of the entity in order to obtain economic efficiency. In order to develop the predictive aspect of management accounting, it is necessary to study and creatively apply the experience of European countries with a well-developed market economy and efficient methods of collecting, processing and using information. In this sense, a significant role belongs to the "direct-costing" method, which facilitates the control over the efficiency of the use of resources and favors the elaboration of transfer prices as an objective tool for evaluating the activity of the production subdivisions. Currently, in addition to the factors that clearly amplify the timeliness of improving management accounting and increases its accessibility for management staff, there are circumstances that, in our view, may facilitate the implementation of the elements of the "direct-costing" method (for example, the presence of deep theoretical elaborations of indigenous scientists, the proliferation of performances of the reform of the national accounting system accompanied by the adoption of new normative acts, etc.). Thus, the management accounting as a whole and the direct-costing system in particular play an important role not only in increasing control over the efficient resource use, but also in developing transfer pricing as one of the most objective evaluation tools of the production subdivisions activity.

At the same time, we consider that without solving the problem of transfer pricing, it is impossible to further reform and improve the relationships within the entities.

The transfer price represents the price based on which the assets or debts are transmitted between the related parties [1], and the transfer prices for agricultural products and additional biological assets are understood as the prices established by the administration of the enterprise (economic section, management accounting department etc.) to the own manufacturing stocks transmitted by a subdivision (branch or sub-branch) to another beneficiary within the entity for subsequent consumption [2].

Among the many transfer pricing methods applied in international practice, the most notorious are the following:

- the method based on the current market prices of the given region. However, in the current conditions of the Republic of Moldova, its application is problematic due to high inflation, lack of organized market for many types of products and economic subjects' insufficient information about price fluctuations;

- the method based on the full or reduced costs of the responsibility centers, depending on the selected variant of the "direct-costing" system. For the subdivisions of the agricultural sectors this method is also not acceptable, because it does not coordinate with the income obtained, while not taking account of the quantity, quality and time taken to obtain the products;

- the method based on contract prices and the partial or complete recovery of fixed costs on account of undervalued marginal income in connection with the absence from the market. Such a method is more universal, but requires additional dexterity, information and labor costs. In its turn, this makes it possible mainly in entities with highly qualified managers and well-organized economic work.

Investigations have shown that with the development of the market economy, interest in transfer pricing (as well as other elements of domestic trade management) has unduly decreased. The arbitrary setting of these prices, as a rule, have led and continue to lead to the disruption of the interests' balance of the owners of the entities and groups of production subdivisions, have undermined the principles of material interest and responsibility of the parties for final work results. As a result, exaggeration (or reduction) of costs and revenues in single production systems has become more common (eg "forage production - milk production"), the gap between the profitability of "supplier" and "consumer" parties has widened, etc.

In the contemporary conditions of development, the collectives in internal cooperation relations must have the right to obtain and use a part of the surplus product created in the form of marginal income or other economic leverage adequate to the particularities of the given entity. It follows that the transfer prices under normal conditions of commercial activity must be higher than the cost of subdivision, but lower than the actual or predicted average marketing price of the commodity production. This objective can be achieved by differentiating the costs into variables and fixed within the implemented "direct-costing" model, as well as by ascertaining more broadly the particularities of each type of stocks used in the entity (quality, profitability, market presence organized for similar products etc.).

Based on the above, we propose to apply in the agricultural entities in the country two options for determining transfer prices:

➤ **first option - in the case of commercial products**, using the following relationship:

$$PT = PR \times (Pvar + Pfix) : 100, \quad (1)$$

where:

PT - is the transfer price of a quintal of commercial products, MDL;

PR - the selling price of a quintal of the same products in case of alienation in favor of third parties, MDL;

P_{var} - the share of variable costs in the cost structure of these products, %;

P_{fix} - the share of fixed costs in the structure of costs related to the manufacture of the products concerned, %.

Table 1 shows a conventional example with initial and calculated data related to the formation of transfer prices for commercial products.

➤ **the second option - in the case of non-commercial products,** using the following relation:

$$PT = PR \times PF: 100 \times (P_{var} + P_{fix}): 100 \times CEU \times VN, (2)$$

where: **PR** - the selling price of a quintal of commercial products of the "consumer" sector, for which the given type of non-commercial products was used (for example, the price of milk in the case of alfalfa green mass), MDL;

PF - the share of feed in the cost structure of livestock products, %;

CEU - the efficiency coefficient of the metabolic energy uses of the given type of feed in the manufacture of specific animal products;

VN - the nutritional value of a quintal of certain types of feed, q nutritional units.

Table 1. Initial and calculated data for the determination of transfer prices for commercial products

Type of products	Sales price of 1 q of products, MDL	Share of variable costs, %	Share of fixed costs, %	Transfer price of 1 q of products, lei
	(PR)	(P_{var})	(P_{fix})	(PT)
Autumn wheat grain	300	72	18	270,00
Sunflower seeds	480	78	14	442,00
Sugar beet rhizocarps	35	75	15	32,00
Grapes of technical varieties	350	70	20	315,00
Seeded fruits	280	71	19	252,00
Whole milk	300	72	14	258,00
Pig mass	3800	76	13	3382,00

The following (Table 2) shows a conventional example with initial and calculated data related to the formation of transfer prices in the case of non-commercial products.

Table 2. Initial and calculated data for the determination of transfer prices for non-commercial feed for bovine animals

Type of feeds	The nutritional value of 1 q of fodder, q units of nutrients	Coefficient of efficiency of metabolic energy use	The selling price of 1 q of milk, MDL	Feed share in milk cost structure, %	Sum of variable and fixed cost weights, %	Transfer price of 1 q of nutrients, MDL
	(VN)	(CEU)	(PR)	(PF)	(Pvar + Pfix)	(PT)
Hay from a mixture of herbs	0,45	0,55	300	48	86	31,00
Autumn wheat straw	0,26	0,46	300	48	86	15,00
Alfalfa green mass	0,22	0,58	300	48	86	16,00
Beet forage	0,11	0,60	300	48	86	8,00
Carrot fodder	0,14	0,63	300	48	86	11,00
Corn silage	0,36	0,59	300	48	86	26,00
Alfalfa hay	0,30	0,56	300	48	86	21,00

It should be noted that the second option can be used to determine transfer prices not only in the manufacture of fodder, but also in other specialized production with the specification of the last two indicators. The proposed methods of elaborating transfer pricing, based on the combination of the requirements of the economic circuit are commensurable with the results of the activity of most responsibility centers, involving their teams in obtaining all types of products (including non-commercial or with low profitability) and ensuring the authentic determination of their contribution to the final results of the activity.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Balan I., Burlea E. Dicționar explicativ de termeni contabili / Толковый словарь бухгалтерских терминов. Chișinău: Tipogr. „Print-Caro”, 2019. 116 p.
2. Balan I., Frecăuțeanu A. Contabilitatea consumurilor și calcularea costului produselor agricole (probleme, concepte, direcții de perfecționare). Chișinău: UASM, 2005. 218 p.
3. Standardele Naționale de Contabilitate, aprobate prin Ordinul Ministerului Finanțelor. Nr. 118 din 06.08.2013. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii